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RIDGE FORMATION IN NEXTSIM

**SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF RIDGES FORMATION
IN A IDEAL SETUP USING NEXTSIM**

by

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1 Introduction

In neXtSIM, the ice compressive strength equation is defined as follows:

$$P_{\max} = Ph^\eta e^{A(1-C)}$$

With :

- P_{\max} - ice strength
- h - sea ice thickness
- C - sea ice concentration
- $P \in \mathbb{R}^+$ - compression factor
- $\eta \in \mathbb{R}^+$ - thickness exponent
- $A \in \mathbb{R}^+$ - concentration factor

The value of P_{\max} sets the ability of the ice to experience permanent deformations through ridging. As described in the constitutive law (cf. figure 1), i.e. the mathematical expression setting the relationship between stresses and deformations, the ice behaves purely elastically when the internal stress within the ice is above the compressive strength (meaning that no deformation remains if the stresses are relaxed), and ridging can occur when the stresses fall below P_{\max} on the normal stress axis σ_N , and then corresponding to permanent deformation of the material. During long simulations, increasing P_{\max} leads to fewer permanent deformations, hence an overall thinner ice. For shorts runs (e.g 3 days), a raise of the compressive strength causes thicker ridging events, which may be counter-intuitive. Indeed, rising the minimum stress needed to ridge reduces the number of ridges, hence increases the localisation of the stress dissipation. So, the same amount of stress is handled by fewer local ridging events, which may lead to sparser but thicker ridges.

This report is focusing on how the next generation sea ice model, neXtSIM, is behaving with respect to the formations of ridges when under compressive load. More

Figure 1: The constitutive law of the ice in neXtSIM. σ_N is the normal stress axis and τ the shear one.

specifically, we study the sensitivity of some model parameters on the properties of the ridges obtained in simulated sea ice thickness field. The considered parameters are in the so-called sea ice strength equation shown above. The simple numerical setup we used will first be introduced. This idealized setup is designed to obtain results that are mostly depending on the parameters while strongly limiting the role that may be played by others interactions. Maps of typical simulated thickness fields will next be presented in order to illustrate the range of ridging behaviours we can get with the neXtSIM model when considering different initial sea ice thickness in the simulation domain. The effects of the value of the compression factor P on the simulated ridge field will then be investigated while keeping the default value for the sea ice cohesion and various initial thickness fields. In the last part, a trivariate (P, C_{lab}, η) sensitivity analysis will be performed on the thickness limit, a quantitative variable that characterizes a crucial change of the ridging behaviour. Overall, this report

gives an overview of the main impact of parameters of the strength equation's on the simulated ridges and their characteristics.

2 Simple setup

The ideal setup of neXtSIM¹ has been used to create a test setup to observe how ridging events occur in neXtSIM. The thermodynamic process have been disabled, to focus on dynamical aspects. The Coriolis force has been zeroed, since it did not have interesting impacts on the result. And finally, a stationary and homogeneous wind has been set blowing toward the North. The simulations were run using two different meshes, both are landless 100 km side cubic boxes, with triangle elements of 1 km side and with the South and North sides closed. However, the Est and West sides are open in one case and closed in the other. The mesh with open left and right sides will be referred as the *channel*, and the other as the *square* (cf figure 2).

Figure 2: The two used meshes, the square on the left and the channel on the right. The green arrows represent the wind.

3 Ridging shape

For a given set of parameters (P , C_{lab} , h_i) - with C_{lab} the cohesion value at the lab scale - ridges can take various shapes. On the figure 3, the thickness map is plotted for numerous

¹Homogeneous initial ice thickness and concentration, stationary and homogeneous forcings.

combination of parameters and for the two meshes.

3.1 Initial thickness

The parameter having the most impact on ridge shape is certainly **the initial ice thickness**. Indeed, for thin ice, there is a wide ridging area where the shape may vary depending of the others parameters: from a dense field, localized at the top of the mesh (cf. figure 3a - $h_i = 10$ cm, and figure 3c - $h_i = 10$ cm) to a very spread ridging area on almost the entire mesh (cf. figure 3a - $h_i = 50$ cm, and figure 3c - $h_i = 50$ cm). All these cases are mostly dominated by shearing and so ridges are slanted regarding of the wind.

With the increasing initial thickness, the map will reach a point where the ice takes on a *V-shape* (cf. figure 3a - $h_i = 100$ cm, figure 3b - $h_i = 25$ cm, cf. figure 3c - $h_i = 125$ cm, figure 3d - $h_i = 25$ cm). This *V-shape* is always the state of the ice just before the thickness limit (cf. part 5.1).

And finally, for an initial ice thickness above the thickness limit (cf. part 5.1), the ice becomes too thick and there are no more movements. There are no more ridging fields either, only a small ridge at the top of the box, perpendicular to the wind (cf. figure 3a - $h_i = 125$ cm, figure 3b - $h_i = 100/125$ cm, cf. figure 3d - $h_i = 100/125$ cm). This case is pure compression, and will not be detailed further (cf. figure 6 where the two extreme cases are illustrated).

3.2 Other parameters

The second main parameter is probably **the cohesion**. In fact, by comparing the figures 3a and 3b, a thickness limit shift can be observed of around 75 cm. Moreover, it seems that the general ridging behaviour is

(a) Square mesh with $C_{lab} = 0.5$ MPa.

(b) Square mesh with $C_{lab} = 2$ MPa.

(c) Channel mesh with $C_{lab} = 0.5$ MPa.

(d) Channel mesh with $C_{lab} = 2$ MPa.

Figure 3: Thickness map after 1 hour of simulation for the Square mesh (left) and the Channel mesh (right), for $C_{lab} = 0.5$ (top) and $C_{lab} = 2$ (bottom). Each column has a different P and each row a different h_i .

also shifted with C_{lab} but further investigation may be required to verify if a variation of C_{lab} only shift the ridging behaviour thickness or if it also slightly changes the ridging shape.

Next, there is the **compression factor** P which slightly changes the ridging behaviour for small cohesion only. Indeed, on the figure 3a - $h_i = 50/100$ cm, and on the figure 3c - $h_i = 100/125$ cm, there are some differences between the three simulations with different P . And on the other side - where there is more cohesion - the impact of the compression factor is nearly negligible (cf. figures 3b and 3d). In the part 5.2, it will be seen that for high values of C_{lab} , the compression need to reaches unrealistic values to have an impact on the ridging shape.

Then, the different boundary conditions of meshes lead to important ridging variations. For the channel mesh - in the shear range of initial thicknesses - the slanted ridges always start from the top left and right corners while there are no particular conditions for the square mesh. This is due to the limit condition breaks - in the channel - that occur on each corners since the top edge is closed and the left/right one are open.

Finally, to characterise the impact of the different parameters, a method to quantify it is needed, and this will be the point of the parts 4 and 5.

4 Compression factor: P

4.1 Observations

Starting by focusing on P impacts with the default cohesion value ($C_{lab} = 2$ MPa) : the thickness map and the thickness distribution were plotted for both the square and channel meshes. Then, for all the square simulations, no matter of the initial ice thickness,

the difference between the thickness distributions are always in the margin of errors, hence no impact of the compressive strength can be observed.

However, for the channel mesh, consequences of P modifications can be observed. Indeed, with initial thicknesses around 25 cm, there are important differences between the three distributions and maps (cf figure 4). As expected (cf part 1), the distribution with the highest value of compression (green), has the thickest ice, next there is the orange one with the middle range P value, and the smallest compression in blue has the thinner ice. The highest P is, the thicker the ice reached can be.

Lets describe the behaviour of the channel. For simulations with ice below 20 cm, the ice remains mainly in one piece with a smooth border, and it leaves the box through the edges. On the figure 5 is illustrated the general ice behaviour in the channel mesh, so for an initial thickness below 20 cm the ice adopts a shape close to the upper diagram. Then, for an initial thickness above 20 cm, two slanted leads start to appear on both sides of a triangular central area. Hence, the ice start splitting in three parts: one main static at the center and two moving parts on both sides which slide against the central one and leave the mesh. On the figure 5, the middle and bottom plot illustrated a partially opened lead and a fully opened one respectively. Furthermore, as the two moving parts are sliding along the central one, the ice is building-up along the lead, that can clearly be seen on the figure 4.

So, how P impacts the channel mesh? On the figure 4, it is clear on the thickness maps that increasing P leads to thicker ice, and this raise is mostly along the two leads. By looking on the thickness distributions over time, one can see that the thickness distributions start to differ when the leads start to open, and the more the leads are well formed, the more the distributions differ.

Figure 4: Thickness distributions after three days - in the channel mesh - with a 25 cm initial ice thickness and the cohesion set to 2 MPa. Three simulations were performed, using different P values, to observe the impact of the compression factor on the sea ice thickness. In the square above the distribution is shown the thickness maps for the three simulations (the thickness scale is identical on the map and the distribution).

So the compression value has consequences when there is a lead. It also appears that P affects the ability to create leads, since for a same thickness², higher compression leads to clearer leads. And, for the cases where h_i is below 20 cm (when there is no more lead) or above 35 cm (when there is no more shear), the compression factor no longer has an impact on the final ice state.

Another interesting observation - not related to what has been said before - is that in the case of $P = 9 \text{ kPa}$, a dilatancy phenomena can be observed. Indeed, in the leads there are pieces of ice that spin around while being stuck between the big plates.

²In fact, by plotting similar figures than the figure 4 for others initial thicknesses, we can see that the initial thickness is the main variable that controls the lead state, but that is not the point here.

4.2 Conclusion

Finally, what are the effects of the compression factor on ridging events for the default cohesion value?

For the channel, the compression value changes the ice thickness along the leads and also the the state of formation of the lead.

Differences in ice thickness along the leads start to appear when the leads are forming. This means that the compression factor will mainly affect the ridging properties when there are building-up events. It seems counterintuitive that increasing P leads to more building-up since building-up is harder with higher compression, but the other terms of the strength equation should not be forgotten! When a lead is formed the ice thickness is drastically reduced, that also causes a diminution of P_{max} through the h^η term. So the ice continues to building-up along the lead since this is where the ice is the weakest

Figure 5: Illustration of the ridging phenomena according to the initial thickness in the channel mesh with $C_{lab} = 2$ MPa. The light blue is the sea ice, while the dark one depicts the ocean. The black lines represent the ridges, with the line's width proportional to the ridge thickness, and the tiny dark lines show the almost continuous field of small ridges. The initial ice thickness is descending with the diagram. The ice is pushed toward the North by the wind, it can come out of the mesh by both right and left sides.

compared to the rest of the map. And the higher the compression factor is, the higher the compressive strength difference will be between lead and non lead area, the more the ice will ridge along the lead, and so on. That is why higher P leads to thicker ridges.

This reasoning also explains why leads are clearer with higher compression. Indeed, the higher P will be, the weaker the ice along leads will be compared to the non-lead ice, the more the stress will be handled by breaking ice around leads. So increasing the compression factor conducts to better lead propagation, hence clearer leads.

For the square, no significative differences were observed no matters of the initial thickness. This is not surprising in light of the previous paragraphs since no lead can appear in the square mesh and the thickness variations come mainly from the strength difference between lead and non-lead ice.

5 Thickness limit: h_L

5.1 Definition

For every set of parameters (P, C_{lab}, η) , there is an initial ice thickness for which the global ice behaviour changes drastically from a mainly shear behaviour - for small initial thicknesses - to a mainly compressive behaviour - for thicker initial ice (cf. part 3). We refer to this **initial thickness limit** between the two behaviours as h_L (see the figure 6 for illustration). Before the limit, the field of ridges is constituted of slanted ridges which are not perpendicular to the forcing (the wind is toward the North), and beyond h_L , only one ridge is formed at the very top of the mesh and perfectly perpendicular to the forcing. This limit appears no matter of (P, C_{lab}, η) , but these parameters can change its value, and as discussed in the part 3 the limit is always preceded by a *V-shape* thickness. Hence the thickness limit is

a good quantitative variable which may help to follow the impacts of each parameters.

Figure 6: Scheme illustrating the sea ice thickness limit h_L between shear ridging (on the top), and pure compression ridging (on the bottom).

5.2 Parameter dependency

After testing the thickness distribution in the part 4, the thickness limit will be the new quantitative variable that will be looked about. On the figure 7, the impact of the set of parameters (P , C_{lab} , η) is tested. The cohesion seems to be the most determining factor for the thickness limit. Which is not surprising since C_{lab} quantify the impact of the shear deformation, and h_L is defined as the maximum thickness for which the shear is predominant. Furthermore, on the left figure is shown different $h_L(C_{lab})$ functions for $P = 1$ kPa, $P = 3$ kPa, and $P = 9$ kPa. And so, it is clear that the compression factor has no impact for large cohesion, in these cases the shear component is so predominant that the compression is not playing any role. Then, with the decrease of C_{lab} , P starts to have impact on the thickness limit, but always a secondary role.

The evanescence of the P 's impact is probably due to the diminishing value of the thickness below one meter. Indeed, because of the term h^η in the compression strength equation, the strength becomes negligible compared to the mean stress value for high cohesion, no matter of P . Hence, P_{max} has consequences on a very small number of points - the only ones whose normal stress is above P_{max} - that may explain the right

side of the figure 7 where all the curve are almost overlaid. To verify this, the thickness limit for a strength value close to the mean normal stress was computed, and the result is the black dot plotted on the figure 7. So in this case, the strength value changes the thickness limit as expected but it can be noticed that even for a large increase of P - its ratio between the red line and the black dot is 33 - the thickness limit is not much changed. Hence, it can be concluded that the compression factor has a minor role in the ridging shape process.

On the left figure, all simulations are made with $\eta = 1.5$, and in the right one is compared run with η between one and two. Then, the impacts of the exponent value can be observed and like the compression factor the thickness exponent has an impact only for small C_{lab} . Moreover, even for small cohesion, the thickness exponent has a minor role on the thickness limit, and the results change by 1 cm at best. So η may be considered as having no role on the ridging behaviour limit.

Finally, a fit is performed using three free parameters including the C_{lab} exponent. The results are shown on the left side of the figure 7, and the numerical values in the legend are the fitted parameters values. A $\frac{-1}{2}$ exponent may be expected for the cohesion but the exponents found are between 0.63 and 0.87 according to the compression value.

6 Conclusion

To understand how the strength equation changes the ridging properties in neXtSIM, a simple setup was built using a 100 km side square mesh with different boundary conditions. A bunch of the basic neXtSIM features were deactivated in order to focus on the ridging events, but the results of this report may be extrapolated to real sim-

Figure 7: Impact of the set of parameter on the thickness limit h_L . On the top is plotted the thickness limit depending of the cohesion C_{lab} for three compression factors P . On the bottom, the same graph is plotted but with different thickness exponent values η in addition.

ulations since some verifications were performed to ensure the invariance of the results in reel cases. During this report it has been seen that depending of the initial thickness, the compression factor, the cohesion and the mesh, ridging can occurs in very different ways: from a very spread field with a lot of slanted ridges to a unique forcing-perpendicular ridge at the top. The parameters that have the most effect on the ridging shape are the initial thickness, the cohesion and the mesh. For the default cohesion, the compression factor has no effect on the ridging shape for the full-closed mesh but for the channel mesh, increasing the compression leads to thicker ridges and better formed leads. Finally, a single scalar parameter was chosen to numerically compare the impact of all parameters. This variable is the initial thickness limit between the shear and compression ridging behaviours. And for the closed mesh, it has been shown that the cohesion has a major role in the thickness limit but does not follow a $\frac{1}{\sqrt{C_{lab}}}$ law as one should expect. Then the compres-

sion factor has a relatively low impact on the limit but its impact rise while the cohesion decreases. And lastly two thickness exponents were tested but their effects are almost non-existent.